

Syntheses of Furano Compounds : Part XLIV. Syntheses of 2-Carboxybenzo[b]Furan-3-Acetic Acid and 3-Carboxybenzo[b]Furan-2-Acetic Acid

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2-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic acid and 3-carboxybenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid have been synthesised. A new synthesis of benzo[b]furan-3-acetic acid, a plant hormone is reported.

THE compounds named in the title were required in a programme aimed at the elaboration of the synthesis of some new heterocyclic systems condensed at the 1, 2-positions of benzo[b]furan. A synthesis of the compounds is described in the present paper.

A synthesis of methyl 2-methoxycarbonylcoumaran-3-acetate(II) by internal Michael reaction on methyl coumarate-O-acetate(I) by adaptation of the work of Koelsch¹ has been achieved.

The compound (II) could not be dehydrogenated to compound (IV) by using Pd-C (10%) in *p*-cymene². However, when subjected to allylic bromination with NBS followed by dehydrobromination using *N,N*-dimethylaniline³, 2-carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic acid(III) was obtained.

The dimethyl ester(IV) signalled resonances at τ 2.2-2.7 (4H, aromatic protons); 6.25, 6.0 (6H, -COOCH₃, -CH₂COOCH₃) and 5.8 (2H, CH₂COOCH₃).

The anhydride(V) of the acid(III) was prepared by reaction with acetyl chloride and this could be converted into the half-ester(VI) by methanolysis. Compound (VI) could also be prepared by controlled hydrolysis of compound (IV). The half-ester on decarboxylation with copper-bronze followed by hydrolysis gave benzo[b]furan-3-acetic acid(VII), a plant hormone^{4,5}.

Ethyl coumarilate⁶ was converted to benzo[b]furan-2-carboxaldehyde^{7,8} following McFadyen and Stevens' method⁹. The aldehyde when subjected to Doebner's reaction¹⁰ with malonic acid gave benzo[b]furan-2-acrylic acid which, in turn, was quantitatively reduced to benzo[b]furan-2-propionic acid(VIII) with sodium amalgam. This acid on cyclodehydration with P₂O₅ gave 1-oxo-1*H*-benzo[b]cyclopenteno[2, 3-*d*]furan(IX). Attempt to prepare 3-carboxybenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid(XI) from compound (IX) by alkaline oxidation¹¹ of the related oxalyl derivative with H₂O₂ proved abortive; the only isolable product was salicylic acid arising by the rupture of the furan ring.

- (III) R=COOH, R₁=CH₂COOH
(IV) R=COOCH₃, R₁=CH₂COOCH₃
(VI) R=COOH, R₁=CH₂COOCH₃
(VII) R=H, R₁=CH₂COOH
(VIII) R=CH₂CH₂COOH, R₁=H
(X) R=CH₂COOCH₃, R₁=COOH, H
(XI) R=CH₂COOH, R₁=COOH

However, 3-ethoxycarbonylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid, prepared according to Koelsch and Whitney¹² from ethyl phenoxycetate and ethyl oxalate, was homologated by Arndt-Eistert procedure¹³ to give (X) which was hydrolysed to the acid (XI). This acid also gave the anhydride(XII) on treatment with acetyl chloride.

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 237. The NMR spectra were recorded in Varian A-60 instrument and in deuterio-chloroform with TMS as internal standard

(chemical shifts are expressed in τ values and J in Hz.).

Methyl Coumarate-O-acetate(I) :

A solution of sodium (1.2 g) in dry methanol (17 ml) was treated with coumarin (7.3 g) and boiled for 10 minutes. Methyl bromoacetate (8.0 g) was then added, and boiling continued for 3 hours. The mixture was then poured into ice water (100 ml), which resulted in separation of an oil. It was left overnight and extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded a colourless thick oil. Distillation of the oil under reduced pressure (b.p. 172-74°/1.75 mm) gave methyl coumarate-O-acetate (8.5 g) as thick colourless liquid which soon solidified. Crystallisation from methanol gave colourless small needles, m.p. 70°. (Found : C, 62.36 ; H, 5.54. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.39 ; H, 5.64%) ; ν_{max} 1630, 1697 and 1755 cm^{-1} .

Methyl 2-Methoxycarbonylcoumaran-3-acetate(II) :

When a solution of sodium (0.12 g) in dry methanol (2 ml) was added to methyl coumarate-O-acetate (6.5 g) at room temperature, the mixture became yellow and its temperature rose considerably. It was then warmed for 15 minutes, cooled and neutralised with acetic acid. The mixture was extracted with ether, ethereal layer washed with dilute Na_2CO_3 solution, water and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent furnished(II) as a thick colourless oil (5.4 g ; b.p. 151-52°/1.5 mm) which solidified. This was crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 55°. (Found : C, 62.29 ; H, 5.48. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.39 ; H, 5.64%) ; ν_{max} 1715 and 1760 cm^{-1} ; NMR(CDCl_3) : τ 2.77-3.16 (4H, aromatic protons) ; 6.27 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_3$) ; 6.2 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$) ; 7.22 (2H, d, $J=4\text{Hz.}$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_3$) ; 5.88 (1H, m, $-\text{CHCH}_2\text{COOCH}_3$) ; 5.05 (1H, d, $J=4\text{Hz.}$, $-\text{CHCOOCH}_3$).

2-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic Acid(III) :

A trace of benzoyl peroxide was added to a mixture of methyl 2-methoxycarbonylcoumaran-3-acetate (1.0 g) and NBS (0.72 g) in dry CCl_4 (50 ml) and the resulting mixture heated on a water bath. The colour of the solution gradually became red. After 4 hours of reflux, the red colour was discharged and hydrogen bromide gas began to appear at the condenser outlet. Refluxing was further continued for one more hour. By that time evolution of hydrogen bromide had ceased. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to obtain a brownish red oil (1.35 g). This was heated for 4 hours with freshly distilled dimethylaniline (16.5 ml) in a metal bath heated at 195-200°. The brownish solution was cooled, taken up in ether and washed thrice with 40

ml portions of well-cooled H_2SO_4 (3N), water and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent left a brown oil which was refluxed for 5 hours with a solution of aqueous methanolic (1 : 1) potash (1.5 g in 20 ml). Methanol was removed from the reaction mixture and the alkaline solution cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The aqueous solution, thus obtained was cooled and just acidified (conc. HCl) to afford a thick brown oil which was discarded. Addition of four to eight more drops of conc. HCl gave second crop of the oil which was also discarded. Further acidification of the solution afforded 2-carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic acid as a light grey solid (0.6 g). This was recrystallised from acetic acid in light grey needles, m.p. 230° (decomp.). (Found : C, 59.87 ; H, 3.61. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.00 ; H, 3.66%) ; ν_{max} 1680 and 1720 cm^{-1} .

The dimethyl ester(IV) obtained as a thick oil was distilled (b.p. 165°/1.75 mm) which solidified at room temperature. Crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) gave cluster of colourless needles, m.p. 88°. (Found : C, 62.88 ; H, 4.69. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.90 ; H, 4.87%) ; ν_{max} 1708 and 1739 cm^{-1} .

2-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic Anhydride(V) :

Compound (III) (0.5 g) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (1 ml) in dry benzene (4 ml) for 4 hours. Removal of the solvent afforded a pale brown solid of the anhydride which on crystallisation from dry benzene was obtained in colourless shining plates, m.p. 199° (decomp.). (Found : C, 65.26 ; H, 3.01. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ requires C, 65.35 ; H, 2.9%) ; ν_{max} 1765 and 1800 cm^{-1} .

Methyl 2-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetate(VI) :

(a) The foregoing anhydride (0.4 g) was refluxed with dry methanol (10 ml) under dry conditions for 4 hours. Removal of the solvent gave the half-ester, crystallised from benzene in cluster of colourless shining needles, m.p. 148°. (Found : C, 61.48 ; H, 4.25. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 61.54 ; H, 4.30%).

(b) Compound (IV) (0.5 g) was refluxed with methanolic potash (1 mol ; 1.12 ml ; 10%) for 20 minutes. Colourless solid obtained after removing methanol was taken up in water, washed with ether and acidified (conc. HCl) to yield a colourless precipitate of the half-ester. This was crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 148°. (Found : C, 61.37 ; H, 4.16. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 61.54 ; H, 4.30%) ; ν_{max} 1665 and 1730 cm^{-1} .

Benzo[b]furan-3-acetic Acid(VII) :

The foregoing half-ester (1.17 g) was mixed with copper-bronze (100 mg) and heated in a metal bath

at 150° for 30 minutes till the evolution of CO₂ was complete. The product on distillation under reduced pressure yielded a light yellow oil (0.9 g). This was heated with NaOH (2 ml ; 10%) for 1.5 hours, cooled and acidified (conc. HCl) to furnish a colourless solid of (VII), This was recrystallised from petroleum ether in flattened white needles, m.p. 89-91° (lit.^{4,5}). (Found : C, 67.90 ; H, 4.38. Calc. for C₁₀H₈O₃ : C, 68.18 ; H, 4.58%) ; ν_{\max} 1710 cm⁻¹.

Benzo[b]furan-2-propionic Acid (VIII) :

Ethyl coumarilate (3.5 g) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (8 ml ; 99%) in ethanol (16 ml) for 5 hours. The hydrazide crystallised from dilute ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 174°. (Found : N, 15.86. C₉H₈O₂N₂ requires N, 15.90%). The hydrazide (2.7 g) in dry pyridine (18 ml) was treated at 0° with tosyl chloride (4.2 g) and after 6 hours the mixture was poured into iced HCl. The tosyl hydrazide derivative separated as cream coloured solid, m.p. 200-201°. (Found : N, 8.36. C₁₆H₁₄O₄N₂S requires N, 8.48%). A solution of the tosyl hydrazide (2.0 g) in ethylene glycol (15 ml) was heated at 160° and anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (3.0 g) added to it in one lot. The vigorous reaction was quenched after 3 minutes by pouring into hot water. The resultant mixture was cooled and extracted with ether to give the benzo[b]furan-2-carboxaldehyde (b.p. 135°/18 mm) (lit.^{7,8}). (Found : C, 73.88 ; H, 4.13. Calc for C₉H₆O₂ : C, 73.96 ; H, 4.14%) ; ν_{\max} 1670 cm⁻¹.

The foregoing aldehyde (1.0 g) and malonic acid (1.5 g) in dry pyridine (3.1 ml) with piperidine (1 ml) were heated for 6 hours, cooled, diluted with water and acidified (HCl) to afford benzo[b]furan 2-acrylic acid (1.3 g), crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 221-22°. (Found : C, 70.06 ; H, 4.12. C₁₁H₈O₃ requires C, 70.21 ; H, 4.29%) ; ν_{\max} 1625 and 1690 cm⁻¹.

The above acid was quantitatively reduced with sodium amalgam (2%) giving benzo[b]furan-2-propionic acid, crystallised from benzene in colourless shining flakes, m.p. 145-46°. (Found : C, 69.30 ; H, 5.18. C₁₁H₁₀O₃ requires C, 69.46 ; H, 5.30%) ; ν_{\max} 1700 cm⁻¹.

Cyclodehydration : Formation of 1-oxo-1H-benzo[b]cyclopenteno[2, 3-d]furan (IX) :

This acid (1.4 g) was treated with P₂O₅ (10.0 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) for 10 hours to give the ketone (IX) which crystallised from benzene in cream coloured shining needles, m.p. 155°. (Found : C, 76.72 ; H, 4.65. C₁₁H₈O₂ requires C, 76.73 ; H, 4.68%) ; ν_{\max} 1700 cm⁻¹.

The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained in blood-red needles from acetic acid, m.p. 301° (decomp.). (Found : N, 15.87. C₁₇H₁₂O₅N₄ requires N, 15.90%).

Attempted Synthesis of 3-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid :

A mixture of (IX ; 0.86 g) and dry ethyl oxalate (0.73 g) was treated with sodium methoxide (from 0.12 g Na) in dry benzene (4 ml) when the colour changed to greenish yellow. The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature resulting in sodium salt of the oxalyl ester which was filtered and treated with KOH (6.0 g) in methanol (30 ml). After 30 minutes, H₂O₂ (15 ml ; 30%) and methanol (20 ml) were added all at once and allowed to stand for further 0.5 hour. After removal of methanol, it was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified (conc. HCl) and extracted with chloroform. Removal of the solvent afforded a colourless solid, m.p. 159°, which was identified as salicylic acid.

Methyl 3-Ethoxycarbonylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetate (X) :

3-Ethoxycarbonylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid (1.4 g) in dry benzene (6 ml) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (2 ml) for 3 hours. The excess of thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the last traces removed by twice successive addition of benzene followed by its removal under reduced pressure. The resulting oily (light yellow) acid chloride in dry ether was added to dry ethereal diazomethane (prepared from nitrosomethylurea, 6.0 g) and left overnight in the refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure to furnish the diazoketone as an orange oil. The diazoketone in dry methanol (30 ml) was heated on a water bath ; to it was added small amount of slurry of silver oxide (0.7 g) in dry methanol (20 ml) and stirred. As soon as the evolution of nitrogen subsided, more of the silver oxide was introduced and this process continued until all the slurry had been added. The mixture was then refluxed for 20 hours. Within this period about 1.4 g of silver oxide was added in instalments. Then the mixture was treated with charcoal, filtered and solvent evaporated to obtain pale yellow oil (0.7 g) (b. p. 130°/0.3 mm) which solidified. Crystallisation from methanol gave pale yellow needles, m.p. 151-52°. (Found : C, 64.02 ; H, 5.41. C₁₄H₁₄O₅ requires C, 64.11 ; H, 5.38%) ; ν_{\max} 1705 and 1755 cm⁻¹.

3-Carboxybenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid(XI) :

The foregoing ester (0.28 g) was heated with NaOH (1 ml ; 10%) for 3 hours, cooled and acidified to furnish compound (XI) in quantitative yield, crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 242°. (Found : C, 59.95 ; H, 3.63. C₁₁H₈O₅ requires C, 60.00 ; H, 3.66%). The anhydride(XII) separated as shining needles from acetyl chloride, m.p. 201-2°. (Found : C, 65.31 ; H, 2.95. C₁₁H₆O₄ requires C, 65.35 ; H, 2.99%) ; ν_{\max} 1765 and 1790 cm⁻¹.

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